

Role of Library Marketing Service in Entrepreneurial Opportunity for Librarians: An Overview

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Abstract

Libraries are known to play the roles of connecting people with their services they required to be successful in all aspects of their lives. Libraries provide information services and expertise couple with new technologies that will assist librarians in entrepreneurial opportunities and business acumen. Librarians as a matter of fact should be actively involved in marketing of library services. Therefore, this paper aims at examining the concepts of libraries, librarians, marketing and library services. The paper also discusses entrepreneurship and its features. It also talks about entrepreneurship opportunities for librarians such as documentary services, abstracting and indexing services to publishers, advert agency, marketing of library and information science products, writing articles, conference papers. Skills required for librarians to thrive in entrepreneurial opportunities are also discussed. The paper also discusses key aspects of marketing information services and the roles of library marketing services in entrepreneurial opportunities for librarians. The paper concludes that there are a lot of entrepreneurial opportunities in which interested librarians can explore the possibilities to start a new venture and become successful, and fulfill their entrepreneurial dreams. Such entrepreneurial opportunities include but not limited to book publishing industry, book distribution agency, periodical subscription agency, newspaper dealership and bookshop.

Keywords: Libraries, Librarians, Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurial opportunities, Market

Introduction

Marketing in the broadest sense ranks as one of the most popular topics of the day. It basically starts with the market research, identifying the consumer needs and demands, their pricing and promoting them to the appropriate consumers. Marketing main idea is to attract and retain a growing base of satisfied customers. Hence, marketing of library services aims at determining the needs, wants and demands of the target clients through designing and delivering appropriate services more effectively for the purpose of achieving organizational goals and objectives as well as creating entrepreneurial opportunities for

librarians in terms of profit making. Marketing of library services is gradually becoming an area which attracts the attention of market researchers, and the business people (Patange, 2013).

Libraries are said to be relatively new to the marketing area. In India for instance, marketing of library services is a new concept and it is not too old when compared to other developed countries. The above said concept has emerged during the early 1970s. Since then, it has gained much attention in the USA and is considered as most important profession. Marketing approach in libraries is mainly useful in improving their image and to attract more and more clientele. It helps librarian to upgrade their innovative

knowledge both within their organizations and as an entrepreneurial opportunity within the society. Most of the librarians view that marketing of products and services is not possible in the profession of librarianship. But, Authors such as Philip Kotler (Marketing Guru) is of the view that marketing is not limited to large corporations seeking profits only. It is equally applicable to non-profit organizations as well as colleges, universities, charitable institutions, libraries, information centers and services organizations also ((Patange, 2013).

Library marketing in a general perspective encompasses a range of activities and approaches aimed at connecting librarians with their target audiences, raising awareness about library's available resources and services, and fostering a positive perception of the role of library services in the society. It involves librarians understanding information seekers' needs, designing effective communication strategies, and employing innovative techniques to engage and attract potential customers. Library marketing services is not limited to traditional promotional methods but also encompasses digital marketing, social media engagement, community outreach, and partnerships with other institutions and organizations (Gruenberg, 2022; Pal, 2022; Julien & Barker, 2022)

The digital age has opened up new entrepreneurial opportunities for librarians in the area of library marketing services, with digital platforms and social media playing a crucial role in reaching and engaging information users. Librarians can leverage social media platforms to share information, promote events, and engage in two-way communication with patrons. Additionally, Acharya and Vagdal (2023) opined that libraries and librarians can utilize digital advertising techniques to target specific user segments and optimize their marketing efforts. Dars and Karn (2008) stated that in a bit to create new ventures, confront challenges associated with the innovations and competitions in information provision and most especially in order to ensure the survival of libraries and librarians, the need for information marketing and entrepreneurial activities emerged to help the librarians to manage better.

1. Library Marketing Services

The history of library marketing services began long before the concept was born. Samuel Swett Green in his often quoted speech at the ALA Conference in 1876 advocated improved personal relations between librarians and readers. It could be said that today's marketing of library services has its roots in parts of the USA and Northern Europe, in countries with few illiterates and more money, libraries, and library schools than the rest of the world. This certainly does not mean that the idea of libraries reaching out to "the common man" has not occupied librarians in other parts of the world (Renborg, 1997).

Chandratre and Chandratre (2015) asserted that marketing as a concept and as a practice still seems unknown to many librarians. Some librarians may feel that marketing is somehow inappropriate for a public service institution such as library and see no room for such practice in a not-for-profit profession like librarianship. Some information service managers feel that marketing is inimical to the nature of their activities. But with increased competition in the world of information, marketing is a factor for survival. At the same time, there is a common misconception that promotional activities alone constitute marketing in library services.

Libraries of all types and sizes are faced with the need to market its services. Therefore, librarians must learn to effectively market and advertise their services. Steadley (2003) pointed out that the following are basic things to know about library marketing services.

- 1. Competition for customers** – information provision centres are part of a highly competitive service industry. Competition comes from mega-bookstores, online book dealers, consultants, the Internet, and individuals who feel they can go it alone. Libraries are no longer the only information show in town. Free web access to information is here to stay and non-library and fee access information providers won't hesitate to market to library customers.

2. **Competition for resources** - Libraries of all types have to compete with other organizations or departments for funds. Public libraries have to vie for public monies that provide for their existence. Special libraries find their funding is frequently targeted during parent organization budget cuts. Library marketing services benefits the bottom line.
 3. **Maintain your relevance** - Libraries need to market themselves to remain connected with their communities and have some bearing on real-world issues and present-day events.
 4. **Stop being taken for granted** - Libraries need to convey what is unique about the access and services they provide. Both customers and librarians cannot assume that libraries will always be available.
 5. **Promote an updated image** - Librarians are not perceived as well-trained, technologically savvy information experts. Most customers do not see the demanding information management responsibilities of a librarian.
 6. **Visibility** - Librarians are not on the radar screens of many people who think of themselves as information literate. People who are in positions to employ librarians are not reading much in their professional literature about a librarian's value.
 7. **Valuable community resource** - Libraries are and should be viewed as essential and valuable community resources. People need to be made aware of the services and products that are provided and their comparative value. Librarians should be the resource that the local power structure goes to for information.
 8. **Rising expectations** - Library users expect recognition, attention, and appreciation for their individual information needs. Customers also have ever-changing needs and wants, which makes the library market as dynamic as retail markets. Marketing helps to create an environment in libraries that fosters customer consciousness among employees.
 9. **Survival** - Libraries depend on the support of others for their existence. A library must communicate and work with its customers and governing/funding entities to provide information about what the library is doing and to enable the library to learn about the community it serves.
 10. **Beneficial to library image** - Effective marketing can among other things: increase library funds, increase usage of services, educate customers and non-customers, change perceptions, and enhance the clout and reputation of the library and its staff.
2. **4Ps of Marketing Mix in Library services**
- There are four key business concepts that provide the basis for marketing thought and action in the nonprofit setting like library. The core of marketing is considered to be the marketing mix. This concept of marketing mix has given due recognition in the marketing theory and the concept of marketing mix which was accepted as the set of marketing tools. It should be noted that the twelve elements of marketing mix has been merged into four elements. The four elements are known as 4ps, which are: Product, Price, Place and Promotion. Product is anything which is offered to the market for exchange of use and it is the most important thing in the marketing system in library services. Some of the products in library services are documentary services, abstracting and indexing services to publishers, advert agency, marketing of library and information science products, writing articles, etc. Pricing is another variable of the marketing mix. It is the most difficult issue. Lot of things is to be kept in

mind while discussing price in relation to library services. Three types of pricing come to mind in library marketing services, which are cost recovery, by which the libraries cover only budgeted cost, commercial pricing, where the library information providers make a profit through provision of library services and premium pricing, in which customers pay more of the services rendered to them by librarians.

The third variable of marketing mix in library services is the place. The place is the process of getting the goods or services from the producer to the consumer. In library services, it is a matter of information distribution and brokerage. It is the channel that links information provision and information users. Promotion is the fourth market mix in library marketing services. It involves one or more, or all, of the following methods to reach the client: direct marketing; public relations; advertising; sales promotion and personal selling. Marketing approach to library services is an endeavor to accelerate the services to provide librarians. It is warned that if the librarians fail to catch hold of the entrepreneurial opportunities, the scene will be captured by the commercial vendors.

3. Entrepreneurship opportunities for Librarians

The concept of entrepreneurship is defined as the process through which entrepreneurs create, nurture and grow enterprises using a reasonable degree of initiative, skills and competencies necessary to transform change into opportunities thereby deriving personal satisfaction, monetary rewards and independence. On the other hand, the concept of library is seen as an institution that support the university community by delivering services to meet the teaching, research and learning needs of staff and students. Libraries are universally recognized as important social institutions and no community is considered complete without a library system. Library can be seen as a valuable institution where individuals and group of people visit to carry out some researches in respect to their various needs. The library is so importance to human development in the sense that it is where knowledge is reserve and waiting to be tapped by researchers, and as such should be given priority. Notwithstanding, economic challenges such as

unemployment has affected the capacity of library students and professional librarians to be self-reliance which necessitated the government and universities to accord priority to entrepreneurship education, skills and awareness among students. (Olufunke, 2017).

According to Awurdi and Mohammed (2018), library plays a key role by providing a variety of services to a wide range of users in the academic environment. University libraries acquire, process, manage and disseminate information resources through which their parent institutions conduct research and produce high-level manpower. Libraries provide access to information resources in diverse formats to users. They provide timely and relevant information in support of teaching and research needs of their parent institutions. The university library is a repository of information resources. These resources are the traditional information resources which include books, journals, maps, encyclopedia, dictionaries, newspapers and periodicals. Some of the services provided are reference services, technical services, selective dissemination of information, lending services, bibliographic services, reprographics services, inter-library loan services, indexing and abstracting services.

Adomi, (2009) opined that career opportunities for Librarians are endless. The tasks for a librarian who wants to engage in a business other than a traditional library is to identify an area and then convince somebody that he is capable of undertaking business ventures. Anyanwu, Oduagwu, Ossai-Onah, and Amaechi, (2013) also stressed that entrepreneurial opportunity exists where there is a need, want, problem or challenges in librarianship that can be addressed, solved and or satisfied in an innovative way. It is about recognition or discovery of new ways of provision of library and information services and allied or information related services. The researchers also offers a comprehensive list of entrepreneurial opportunities available for librarians, which includes library equipment business, publishing and printing business, information brokerage business, courier services business, library consultancy business, rural information provision business, stationary

business, reprographics business, art gallery business, vendor business freelance information business.

In addition to entrepreneurial opportunities for librarians, Batthini (2020) list the following as few entrepreneurial opportunities for Librapreneurs, in which interested librarians may explore the possibilities to start a new venture and become successful and fulfill their entrepreneurial dreams. They include; book publishing industry, book distribution agency, periodical subscription agency, newspaper dealership, book shop, stationary shop, binding workshop, lending library, reading room, consultancy services, career counselor, library software developing industry, online bookstore, digital book/periodical publishing, subscription agency of electronic book/journals, writing biographies

Other entrepreneurial opportunities for Librarians as stated by Lucky and Ugheh, (2014) include; internet search service to co-workers especially in academic environment, computer programmer, cyber cafe operator/manager, working in telecom companies such as GLO, Airtel, MTN, Documentary services, abstracting and indexing services to publishers, advert agency, marketing of library and information science products, writing articles, conference papers, organizing workshops for librarians and digitization of library materials as well as book reviewing. The researchers further opined that each of the entrepreneurial opportunities required Librarians to develop professional knowledge and skills to provide the above services to people effectively and efficiently in the society. But however, other areas that can be engage includes tutorial classes and coaching centers, establishment of nursery schools for children, laundry and dry-cleaning services, operating stores and supermarkets or fast food joint, indoor and outdoor catering services, cake baking, wedding designer and water factories for packing and repackaging.

4. Skills required by librarians for entrepreneurship to thrive

Skills are abilities or proficiency required of a person in a position to plan and execute an action geared towards accomplishing some tasks or

achieving some goals. Skills are the learned capacity to carry out predetermined tasks with the minimum outlay of time and energy. Entrepreneurs must endeavour to possess the applicable skills in order to succeed in any business venture. It is important to note that traditional roles are becoming less frequent in the array of entrepreneurial careers now open to information professionals. As a result, different competencies, skills and graduate qualities are required for entrepreneurship (Elonye & Uzuegbu, 2013). Ugwu and Ezeani (2012) identified the following skills that must be acquired by library professional entrepreneurs towards successful entrepreneurship venture:

- a) **Information Technology Skills:** These include networking, library automation and digitization, web-based services, reprography, micro-graphs, facsimile, video text, teletext, database creation and management systems including CDS, ISIS, LIBSYS, content development, desktop publishing, internet, presentation, hardware/software skills and relational databases including the ability to create data structures which facilitate the indexing and retrieval of information and thesaurus development.
- b) **Information Literacy Skills:** These have to do with the ability to locate information efficiently and effectively, evaluate information critically and competently and using information accurately and creatively. Also included here is the economics and marketing of information products and services, information resource management, information processing and organizing, e-mail, multimedia perspectives and video conferencing.
- c) **Managerial Skills:** These are the business management skills such as marketing, financing, accounting, control, planning and goal setting, decision making, human relations and managing growth. These are essential in launching and growing a new venture.
- d) **Personal entrepreneurial skills:** These include inner control/discipline, risk taking, inventiveness, change orientation

- and ability to manage change, persistence, and visionary leadership.
- e) **Technical Skills:** Written and oral communication, interpersonal, monitoring environment, the ability to organize, and network building. These skills are necessary for successful venture and they should be given attention by students to enable them succeeding in venturing.

Aside the above stated skills required by librarians for entrepreneurship to thrive, Chandratre and Chandratre (2015) opined that librarians must embrace the cross-channel experience when providing information service and work with information users to find the most useful channel for their purposes. The authors stated that strategic planning is required for a librarian to achieve success in marketing of information. Strategic planning involves formulation of vision, mission and goals setting. It may involve market research where the librarian can do the following:

1. Understanding his client, which is known as market research
2. Identifying his client market i.e. segment and target
3. Identifying his entrepreneurial strengths as competitive business
4. Knowing the services his clients want and where they want to use it
5. Developing effective and efficient procedures and systems that facilitate outcomes for clients
6. To employ and train staff in both work skills and client relationship marketing
7. To communicate the benefits and advantages of his services over competitors

5. **Difficulties Librarians encounter in Library Marketing Services**

Most librarians do not market their information resources because they do not know how to market, or do not know how carry out the marketing effectively.

1. **Being Reluctant** - Too often librarians wait for others to notice that they are doing a good job. Librarians may be

reluctant to capitalize on their strengths and knowledge, while the general public often does not see the value that information professionals could bring to sophisticated information challenges.

2. **Wrong Belief** - There is a belief that information products do not need to be marketed in any special way because their importance to society should be visible to all.
3. **Inadequate training and education** - Often librarians do not market their services well due to lack of training and knowledge of marketing tools and techniques. Despite the growing literature on library marketing, there remains a lack of familiarity with the total marketing concept among librarians.
4. **Fear** - Librarians are often reluctant to borrow from the private sector. They have a fear of commercial publicity and see marketing as manipulative, a waste of time and resources, and unprofessional.
5. **Nonchalant attitude of librarians** - Rather than selling information on its value and letting people know what they can offer, librarians often wait for customers to come to them. Rather than pushing out responses to anticipated information needs to customers, librarians wait for customers to stop by the facility or stumble across the information web site.
6. **Complex and complicated task** - Marketing is a complicated problem for librarians because of their wide range of products and services from books to Internet access, and an extremely diverse audience that ranges from children to seniors, public officials to business people, and the society at large.
7. **Money and attitude** - Lack of funds is often used as a reason or excuse not to market. However, marketing library

services is not simply a matter of spending dollars on promotion and advertising. Marketing is also a matter of improving the customer's experience of information provision services. The attitude of librarians as they interact with customers is what shapes customers' experiences and 'markets' the information to those customers.

Conclusion

There is no doubt that nowadays, information services are viewed as marketable services, hence librarians have started seeing information users as potential customers. As earlier mentioned that marketing is comprehensive term that describes all the processes and interactions that result in satisfaction for users and revenue for the information firm. Therefore, the need for effective marketing and inclusion of entrepreneurial activities has become necessary for the growth and development of libraries and librarians. The extent of library marketing services determines various other issues including: the patronage of information users; business funding; the visibility and the satisfaction of both the information users and the librarians. Librarians must know their audience to market their services to. Librarians should be innovative, exploring new technologies and noble ideas in the relentless pursuit of excellence. They should embrace the entrepreneurial spirit. The librarians and other entrepreneurs share certain characteristics including creativity, persistence and passion, Librarians can achieve entrepreneurship success through strategic planning. Librarians should explore numerous entrepreneurship skills in order to become self-sustaining and society impacting in the knowledge economy.

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